

Analyzing the Role and Liability of Paramedics in the Indian Healthcare System

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ABSTRACT

The Nursing and staff serves as backbone of a healthcare system. Despite being central to any healthcare system, not much has been written about them, especially on the issue of their regulations and legal liabilities emanating from their professional activities. Though they are governed by National and State councils, the implications of their acts are different in Civil Law, Criminal Law and under their respective regulations. These differences are primarily the subject matter of this paper.

KEY WORDS: nursing; nursing staff; nursing negligence; consumer protection Act

INTRODUCTION:

The role of nursing staff in healthcare sector cannot be ignored. Starting from the task of providing emergency care, their task ends only with the discharge of the patients. Nursing staffs are involved in many ways at different levels. Besides providing direct patient care, they are continuously involved in non-nursing activities in all the health care setups, viz managing data of various nature in hospital, indentifying the medications, maintaining inventories, managing home keeping activities etc. In addition, communication and interpersonal skills also play an important role in their profession.

The burden of providing these multifold services due to shortage of staff involvement in non nursing jobs, inadequate leadership and poor policies contribute towards burn out among nursing staff which in turns leads to diminished quality of services.

The proper completion of these tasks is essential to provide quality healthcare delivery to the patients. Even a very minute mistake while accomplishing these tasks may lead to serious complications and decides the quality patients care rendered by hospitals.

In light of this, the nursing staff must be aware

of all the possible liabilities that might be incurred while practicing their profession. The current research paper is an attempt to highlight the same.

Considering their importance in the healthcare system, it becomes extremely important to regulate their profession and to establish a minimum standard of conduct. Such regulation becomes all the more important when the paramedics lack awareness regarding their liabilities and the rights of the patient. It is worth considering that as per 2013 study; the legal awareness of the nurses on various legal provisions applicable to them was found as 'poor'⁽¹⁾. In this backdrop, the next section talks about the regulation of nursing staff, especially in the State of Madhya Pradesh.

REGULATION OF NURSING SECTION IN THE STATE OF MADHYA PRADESH:

As the subject of 'public health, hospitals' are in the State List, the responsibility of regulating Nursing becomes a State responsibility. Pursuant to this, several States have established Nursing Councils to regulate their professional conduct in their respective states. Similarly, in the State of Madhya Pradesh, a council named as Madhya Pradesh Nursing Council (hereinafter referred to as 'the Council') has been established under Section 3(1) of the Madhya Pradesh Nursing Education Council Act, 2003. Under the Act, the Council is required to both maintain the State register of nursing practitioners⁽²⁾ and to regulate the nursing Education in the State. Further, the Council is also required to prescribe a code of ethics for regulating the professional conduct of registered

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nurses by appropriate regulations^[41]. Apart from maintaining the State register and prescribing a code of ethics, the Council is empowered to “to reprimand a registered nurses to suspend or remove the name from the State Register or to take such other disciplinary action against him/her, as may, in the opinion of the Council, be necessary or expedient”^[41].

As per Section 39 of the Act, every person possessing a recognized qualification is eligible for enrollment in the State Register. However, the Council may prohibit such entry or remove an existing entry from the State Register of a person who has been “found guilty of infamous conduct in any professional respect by a majority of two-third of the members of the Council present and voting at the meeting”^[41].

However, an order removing or prohibiting from entry shall be made only after giving a reasonable opportunity to the person concerned. The Act also allows an aggrieved person to appeal from such an order to the State Government within ninety days and the decision of the State Government thereon shall be final^[41].

REGULATION OF NURSES IN THE STATE OF MADHYA PRADESH:

The registration and recognition of Nurses in the State of Madhya Pradesh is governed by the Indian Nursing Councils Act, 1947 and the Madhya Pradesh Upcharika, Prasavika, Sahai Upcharika-Prasavika Tatha Swasthya Paridarshak Registrakaran Adhinyam, 1972 (hereinafter referred to as 'State Act'). The State Act establishes Madhya Pradesh Nurses Registration Council^[42] which is required to maintain a State Register of Nurses, Midwives, Auxiliary Nurse Midwives and health Visitors^[42]. Every person possessing the required qualifications is eligible for registration and once registered, he shall be entitled to practice^[42]. However, his/her name may be liable to be removed from the register in case he was convicted by a Criminal Court for any defect in character or if he was found guilty for any infamous professional conduct^[42]. Recently in 2020, the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare has also circulated a draft National Nursing and Midwifery Commission Bill, 2020 to repeal the Indian Nursing Council Act, 1947. The Bill intends to set up a National Nursing and Midwifery Commission, State Nursing and Midwifery Commission among other authorities^[42].

LIABILITY UNDER THE TORT LAW:

One of the most landmark case describing the liability of doctors is Bolam V. Friern Hospital

Management Committee^[43]. In the instant case, the defendant/doctor while treating the plaintiff/patient used electro-convulsive therapy without using relaxant drugs and without using any manual control method. During this treatment, the patient suffered an acetabular fracture and it was alleged that the same was attributed to the negligence of the defendant who failed to take proper precautions. It was alleged that if the defendant had used the relaxant drugs or the manual control or a combination of both, the fracture could have been avoided.

The Court, analyzing the contours of negligence, highlighted two kinds of situations. In the first situation which does not involve any special skill, the negligence meant “Some failure to do some act which a reasonable man in the circumstances would do, or doing some act which a reasonable man in the circumstances would not do; and if that failure or doing of that act results in injury, then there is a cause of action”^[43].

But in the second situation which requires a special skill or competence, the test involves the “standard of the ordinary skilled man exercising and professing to have that special skill”. In such a situation, it is sufficient if the person concerned exercises the “ordinary skill of an ordinary competent man exercising that particular art”^[43].

Finally, with respect to the liability of the doctors, the Court held that “a doctor is not guilty of negligence if he has acted in accordance with a practice accepted as proper by a responsible body of medical men skilled in that particular art”^[43] at the relevant time. This is known as Bolam Test and it has been regularly used to determine the liability of the doctors. The same standard will also be applicable in the cases of nurses.

LIABILITY UNDER THE CONSUMER PROTECTION LAW:

The issue regarding the liability of doctors under the Consumer Protection Act was discussed in the case of Indian Medical Association v. V.P. Shantha & Ors^[20].

The primary question with which the Court grappled in the instant case was whether the services rendered by a medical practitioner, hospital or nursing home can be regarded as 'service' under Section 2(1)(o) of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986. Answering it in the affirmative, the Court concluded that the services by way of consultation, diagnosis and treatment (both medicinal and surgical) rendered by the medical practitioner would come within the meaning of 'service' as defined under Section 2(1)(o) of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986.

However, services that are rendered free of charge or under a contract of personal service are exempted from the same^[21]. Similarly, medical services rendered free of charge by a non-Governmental hospital/Nursing home would be exempted from the purview of 'service' under Section 2(1)(o) of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986. On the contrary, if such medical services are charged then they would fall within Section 2(1)(o) of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986. The Court further added that the liability under the Consumer Protection Act, 1986 would be in addition to any disciplinary action that can be initiated against the medical practitioner by the Medical Council of India (now National Medical Commission) or State Medical Councils.

The issue of negligence by a nurses arose directly in the case of *Jatinder Kumar V. Rattan Lal & Ors.* In this particular case, the doctor advised a malaria parasite slide test to be conducted on the patient however the same was not performed by the nursing staff of the concerned hospital.

The Court remarked that it was the duty of the nursing staff to bring the required samples to the laboratory for the necessary tests and on such failure; the hospital will be vicariously liable for the acts of the nursing staff. However, in case the hospital was liable to pay any compensation for the negligent act of the nursing staff, the hospital can proceed against the negligent nurse as per the law. But the hospital cannot abdicate itself from its liability to pay compensation to the complainant for the negligent act of its nursing staff^[22].

Similarly, the case of *Civil Surgeon-cum-Chief Superintendent and Anr. V. Varsha Chachlani*, directly deals with the negligence by a nursing staff. In the instant case, the patient suffering from chest pain was admitted to District Hospital in the morning. The duty doctor examining him, at around 8:25 AM, instructed the nurse to run ECG, X-Ray Chest, Blood and Urine Test. Similar instructions were also made around 11:00 AM by another medical specialist. However, no tests were conducted till 2:00 PM and the patient died around 2 : 30 PM. Consequently on a case filed by the wife of the deceased patient to the National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, the Commission held the Hospital vicariously liable for the negligence of the doctor and the staff nurse^[23]. In another case, where a staff nurse negligently injected an injection to the patient resulting in paralysis to his left arm, the State Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, Maharashtra held the Hospital vicariously liable^[24].

LIABILITY UNDER THE CRIMINAL LAW:

The Indian Penal Code, 1860 is the primary legislation that provides for the criminal liability of the doctors. Section 88 of the Code, protects the doctors from any harm caused by their acts if such harm was caused with the consent of the patient and for his benefit in the good faith. Further, even acts done without consent in the good faith for the benefit of a person in certain circumstances are exempted from criminal liability^[25].

On the other hand, Section 304A of the Code punishes a doctor for causing the death of a person by doing any rash or negligent act. One of the important cases that discuss the criminal liability of the doctors is *Jacob Mathew v. State of Punjab & Ors.*^[26]. One of the primary questions that the Court was asked to decide in this particular case was whether a different standard is applicable for recording a finding of negligence when a professional, in particular, a doctor is involved. Answering it in the affirmative, the Court held that the negligence in the context of medical profession should be treated differently^[27]. The Court also confirmed the Bolam Test and stated that:

“A simple lack of care, an error of judgment or an accident, is not proof of negligence on the part of a medical professional. So long as a doctor follows a practice acceptable to the medical profession of that day, he cannot be held liable for negligence merely because a better alternative course or method of treatment was also available or simply because a more skilled doctor would not have chosen to follow or resort to that practice or procedure which the accused followed”^[28].

The Court further made a distinction between negligence in civil law and negligence in criminal law. It held that the negligence would not amount to an offence if there was a lack of mens rea and the degree of negligence was lower. Negligence that lacks mens rea or a higher degree may give rise to civil liability but it will not provide a ground for prosecution under the criminal law. The Court, recognizing the nature of interests served by doctors in a particular society, asked to protect them from vexatious or frivolous prosecutions^[29].

However, in a recent case, the Supreme Court highlighted the need to evolve the Bolam Test^[30]. The Court, raising doubts about the Bolam test, remarked that “in a specific case where unreasonableness in professional conduct has been proven with regard to the circumstances of that case, a professional cannot escape liability for medical negligence merely by relying on a body of professional opinion”^[31].

CONCLUSION:

The same tests and legal principles as used in the cases of doctors are applicable when such negligence results from the acts of a paramedic and nursing staff. However, as seen in the case discussed, the complainant or the aggrieved person is entitled to proceed against the hospital when the negligence is by a paramedic and nursing staff. The hospital can, no doubt, take lawful actions against the paramedical and nursing staff but it will also be vicariously liable for the acts of such staff employed by it.

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